

Tree size diversity can enhance the drought resilience of *Abies alba* Mill. in the European mountain forests

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Uneven-aged silviculture
Silver fir
Mountain mixed forests
Growth limiting factors

ABSTRACT

The increasing frequency and severity of extreme events, such as drought, are expected to disturb forest ecosystems worldwide. Stand structure, including tree size diversity, may play a crucial role in how forests respond to these changes. This study examines the effect of tree size diversity on the drought resilience of silver fir (*Abies alba* Mill.) using data from 138 circular plots in even- and uneven-aged mountain stands across Germany, Italy, and Poland. Increment cores from nearly 600 trees were evaluated to calculate complementary resilience indices. Generalized linear mixed-effect models were fitted to assess how tree size diversity affects individual tree growth response to drought stress under varying environmental conditions, mediated by admixture of broadleaf species, stand density, and individual tree size. We found that tree size diversity improves the growth response of silver fir to drought stress, expressed by higher resistance and stress-driven deviation (SDD) indices, in more water-limited sites. However, this benefit diminishes or becomes slightly negative with increasing climate humidity. Similarly, smaller trees demonstrated higher resistance and SDD, although these effects also weakened with more favorable water conditions. The admixture of broadleaf species and stand density did not mediate the impact of tree size diversity on growth resilience. Our results are in line with the stress-gradient hypothesis. Ecophysiological adaptations to prevailing conditions can lead to different competition regimes (symmetric and asymmetric), causing variations in the impact of stand structure on drought resilience. Since tree size diversity is crucial in water-limited environments, it can be considered a strategic forest management tool for adapting silver fir-dominated forests to anticipated global changes.

1. Introduction

Ensuring balanced forest management that meets timber demand, preserves ecosystem functions, and maintains a high level of stability in the face of global change is one of the main challenges in European forestry today. It is crucial to understand how current silvicultural systems and resulting stand structures might influence ecological processes and how to use those systems as tools to sustain ecosystem services provisioning.

Forest management systems have been traditionally classified into

two types: even-aged and uneven-aged, also referred to as multi-aged (O'Hara, 2014; Pommerening et al., 2024). Even-aged silviculture, which has been extensively used in Europe for more than 200 years, entails creating uniform, single-layered stands through large canopy openings (>0.5 ha), often followed by artificial regeneration and intermediate thinning from below (Kuuluvainen et al., 2012; Nyland, 2016) or crop tree thinning (Abetz, 1974; Schädelin, 1942). In contrast, uneven-aged management promotes structurally diverse forests with multiple age classes and layers (O'Hara, 2014), utilizing techniques like single-tree selection and small-group fellings to modify the forest canopy

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2025.122765>

Received 29 October 2024; Received in revised form 25 March 2025; Accepted 28 April 2025

Available online 9 May 2025

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and increase stand spatial diversity (Kuuluvainen et al., 2012; Schütz, 2002). While system classification can be helpful for simplification, it should not constrain forest management outcomes (O'Hara, 2014). The approach to complex silviculture has evolved towards a spectrum of stand structural diversity and moving beyond the traditional dichotomy (Bradshaw, 1992; O'Hara, 2014).

Forest structural diversity encompasses the horizontal and vertical distribution of components within a stand and is a measure of spatial entropy (LaRue et al., 2023). From a practical standpoint, this diversity is typically quantified by assessing tree size diversity and distribution, most commonly the diameter at breast height (DBH) distribution. Pioneered by Liocourt's (1898) research, the 'reverse J' DBH distribution pattern in uneven-aged forests indicates a steady-state distribution essential for long-term sustainable management (Lundqvist, 2017; Picard and Gasparotto, 2016).

The increasing frequency and intensity of drought stress have become pressing concerns, disrupting forested ecosystem stability (Brodrribb et al., 2020). Drought stress leads to reduced growth rates and frequently results in the mortality of individual trees, groups of trees, or even the dieback of entire forest stands (Boczoń et al., 2018). Several theories address how ecosystem processes and properties may respond to various silvicultural systems and resulting structural diversity. Recent advances in understanding resilience emphasize the importance of risk dispersion and developing stable forest ecosystems to effectively navigate future uncertainties (Colfer and Kanninen, 2008). Resistance and resilience to drought stress can be improved through species mixing by promoting asynchronous resource acquisition and stress responses (Pretzsch et al., 2013) or through reducing competition by regulating stand density (total basal area) through thinning operations (Giuggiola et al., 2013; Misson et al., 2003). However, while the evidence that tree species diversity and stand density impact forest ecosystem functioning is growing (Giuggiola et al., 2013; Grossiord, 2020; Jankowski et al., 2024; Pretzsch et al., 2013), the specific effects of tree size diversity are only now being explored (Dănescu et al., 2016; Gazol and Camarero, 2016; LaRue et al., 2023). Similarly to species mixing (Pretzsch, 2014), tree size diversity may lead to changes in growing space allocation via vertical and horizontal spatial clustering, below- and aboveground niche partitioning, and complementarity between trees of different sizes (Ali, 2019; Forrester, 2019; LaRue et al., 2023). Regional peculiarities moderate tree size diversity impact and strongly vary across biomes, forest types, and species, instigating inconsistent results among existing studies (Forrester, 2019). Comprehensive research on the most ecologically and economically important tree species with a design to specifically cover this gap is required.

This study focuses on *Abies alba* Mill., commonly known as silver fir, one of the most abundant coniferous species in the European mountain forests (Desplanque et al., 1999). Silver fir is able to tolerate high temperatures and withstand the unfavorable effects of drought stress better compared to other species occupying a similar ecological niche, such as the Norway spruce (Vitali et al., 2017; Zang et al., 2014), suggesting that it has substantial potential to expand its share within forested areas under projected global warming scenarios (Vitasse et al., 2019). Recent paleoecological studies also indicate the broad presence of silver fir in the past across territories characterized by significantly warmer climates (Tinner et al., 2013). Despite this, extreme drought events (such as the summer drought in 2018 in Central Europe) may lead to the reduction of the stability of the silver fir-dominated forests (Gbur et al., 2025; Schuldt et al., 2020).

Silver fir has excellent plasticity and adaptability to light regimes due to its life strategy, particularly its exceptional epinastic control. In conditions of light scarcity, silver fir favors an "umbrella-shaped" or excurrent crown shape, which, combined with its needles' functional adaptability, enables it to withstand long-term suppression and lack of light (Brzeziecki and Kienast, 1994; Dobrowolska, 2008; Dobrowolska et al., 2017; O'Hara, 2014; Tucker et al., 1987). Silver fir also forms forest stands of varying structures, making it an excellent candidate for

uneven-aged and mixed forest management. Therefore, silver fir is a suitable model tree species to advance our understanding of the relationship between tree size diversity, shaped by different silvicultural systems, and drought resilience (Manetti and Cutini, 2006; Mazza et al., 2014). While some studies have linked silvicultural systems and structural diversity to silver fir growth stability and resilience, findings remain inconsistent (Dănescu et al., 2018).

Therefore, we explore how tree size diversity affects the growth resilience of individual silver fir trees in different forest stand structures under drought stress. We aim to determine whether there is a general relationship between tree size diversity and growth resilience to drought stress and if climatic conditions, other forest stand characteristics (including admixture and stand total basal area), or individual tree size mediate this relationship.

To address the research objective, we tested the following hypotheses (Fig. 1):

H1: Tree size diversity improves the growth resilience of silver fir trees to drought stress.

H2: The effects of tree size diversity on drought resilience vary across climatic gradients.

H3: The effects of tree size diversity on drought resilience are mediated by the admixture of broadleaf tree species and stand total basal area.

H4: Smaller silver fir individuals have higher growth resilience to drought stress.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study sites and data acquisition

We established 138 circular plots, each spanning 0.05 ha, across four sites in Germany, Italy, and Poland (Fig. 2, Table 1) in comparable eutrophic site conditions according to the Polish national site classification (Kliczkowska, 2004). This distribution covers a substantial portion of the natural range of silver fir. The selected sites represent a range of climatic conditions: from marginal populations with water scarcity in the Holy Cross Mountains (PL1), optimal conditions in the Low Beskid Mountains (PL2) and South Tyrol, Italy (IT1) to water-rich sites in the Bavarian Alps, Germany (GE1). This gradient provides a suitable basis for evaluating the effects of tree size diversity on silver fir growth resilience under varying growth-limiting factors. Further details on the study sites are available in Kolisnyk et al. (2024a).

At each site, 34–36 circular plots were established to capture two gradients: the first gradient is tree size diversity, from simple even-aged stands through two-aged and more irregular stand structures to structurally complex, uneven-aged forest stands (Fig. 3, vertical axis). The second gradient is the admixture of broadleaf tree species (Fig. 3, horizontal axis), primarily European beech (*Fagus sylvatica* L.). This approach ensures that the plots comprehensively represent a range of compositional and structural variations across the sites.

Tree positions were recorded in a three-dimensional local coordinate system. Species identity, diameter at breast height (DBH), and any information about tree damage were recorded for all trees with a DBH of 7 cm or larger. Heights were measured for selected trees from different social strata to facilitate the subsequent reconstruction of the heights of the remaining trees.

The management of silver fir-dominated stands across the study sites has transitioned from clear-cutting to shelterwood and selection systems in recent decades. In PL1 and PL2, low-intensity, high-frequency single-tree selection dominates, while in DE1, foresters employ high-intensity, low-frequency interventions targeting the upper layer. IT1, due to the challenging terrain, has the lowest intervention frequency and intensity. Study plots include pre-mature (40–80 years) and mature (100–140 years) even-aged stands. Uneven-aged and transition stands comprise multiple generations, from 15-year-old understory trees to some overstorey individuals exceeding 150 years. PL1, PL2, and DE1 are state-

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of formulated hypothesis (H1-H4).

source: European Forest Genetic Resources Programme (EUFORGEN, source: <https://www.euforgen.org/species>).

Fig. 2. The location of study sites (red rhombi) and distribution of *Abies alba* Mill. in Europe (grey shaded area), source: European Forest Genetic Resources Programme (EUFORGEN, source: <https://www.euforgen.org/species>).

managed, while IT1 has mixed ownership.

Increment cores, taken from around 600 healthy silver fir trees, were used for the analysis. Increment cores were collected from one direction perpendicular to the slope of the hill to avoid reaction wood. In even-aged stands, 3–4 silver fir trees closest to the plot center were cored. In uneven-aged and transition stands, 4–6 cores were taken from trees of different strata. The increment cores were stored in wooden plates for transportation, air-dried, glued to wooden plates, polished in two steps (first using 120-grit sandpaper, then 800-grit sandpaper on the belt sanding table), and scanned at fine resolutions (ranging depending on

ring visibility from 1200 to 2400 dpi). Tree ring width (TRW) was measured and cross-dated using CooRecorder and CDendro software (Maxwell and Larsson, 2021) with an accuracy of 0.01 mm. The tree ring width series length varies across sites. In PL1, chronologies range from 24 to 141 years, averaging 75 years. In PL2, they span 25–158 years, with a 70-year average. IT1 ranges from 24 to 239 years (average 95), while DE1 spans 23–169 years (average 106).

For IT1 and GE1, daily data from the ensembled version of the E-OBS temperature and precipitation data sets (Cornes et al., 2018) with a resolution of 0.1 degrees were used. For PL1 and PL2, due to the

Table 1
The general characteristics of the study sites.

Site	Elevation	Average annual temp. (C)	Sum of annual precipitation (mm)	Total basal area (m ² ha ⁻¹)	Admixture of broadleaf species (%)
Tissens-Laurein, Italy (IT1)	1050–1750 (1320)	3.1– 8.8 (6.8)	642–1336 (894)	29.8 – 90.5 (53.4)	0 – 34.3 (13.9)
Inzel, Germany (GE1)	820 – 1140 (920)	6.2 – 8.5 (7.6)	1471–2081 (1805)	40.7 – 70.1 (54.4)	0 – 35.7 (11.5)
Zagnansk, Poland (PL1)	320–400 (350)	6.7–9.1 (8.1)	608 – 1003 (749)	21.1 – 46.9 (34.1)	0 – 36.5 (13.0)
Nawojowa, Poland (PL2)	580 – 820 (650)	5.9–8.4 (7.0)	731 – 1522 (989)	31.0 – 62.9 (45.4)	0 – 58.8 (15.3)

Note: Values on the left indicate the minimum across plots for the selected years, on the right the maximum, and in parentheses the mean. For IT1 and GE1, climatic data refer to 2001–2020; for PL1 and PL2, 2001–2019.

Fig. 3. Plot selection matrix illustrating tree size diversity (vertical axis) and the admixture of broadleaf tree species (horizontal axis). This design guided plot selection in the field to ensure that plots at each site represent a range of compositional and structural gradients. The DBH distribution represents the theoretical diameter at breast height distribution for each stand structural type.

tendency of E-OBS data to underestimate precipitation in eastern Europe, specifically central Poland, data from the gridded 2 km G2DC-PL+ dataset (Piniewski et al., 2021) were used.

2.2. Data processing

2.2.1. Drought identification and long-term climatic conditions

To assess the impact of drought on ecosystem functioning, it is essential to identify drought events objectively (Schwarz et al., 2020; Slette et al., 2019; Van Loon et al., 2016). Given the ability of trees to adapt phenologically and genetically to changing environmental conditions (Bussotti et al., 2015; Csilléry et al., 2020), this study examines how temporal variations in relative water availability influence growth resilience. Thus, we focus on meteorological drought, defined as a prolonged period of below-average precipitation that disrupts the water balance, leading to reduced soil moisture and increased evapotranspiration deficits (Andrews et al., 2020; Sadiqi et al., 2022; Schwarz et al., 2020; Van Loon et al., 2016). We calculated the Standardized Precipitation-Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI) using “SPEI” R package version 1.8.1 (Beguería and Vicente-Serrano, 2023) for selected time windows (Supplementary 1). Years were identified as drought stress years when at least two of the three selected SPEI variations had values

below -1.5 (Supplementary Table 1). This approach is advantageous considering the wide climatic gradient in this study. For example, the highest precipitation in PL1 over the last 20 years is much lower than the lowest in GE1. The identified years must be termed dry, relative drought years, or drought stress rather than drought years. The study covers the period 2001–2020 for DE1 and IT1 and 2001–2019 for PL1 and PL2, based on the availability of climatic data. Besides, stand management within the plots is well-documented for this timeframe. Including earlier years could introduce bias, as stand structure is the subject of constant change.

To characterize climate humidity in absolute terms and quantify long-term climatic conditions across study sites, we used a singular metric, namely the Forest Aridity Index (FAI) developed by Führer et al., (2011) (Eq. 1).

$$FAI = 100 \times \frac{T_{VII-VIII}}{P_{V-VII} + P_{VII-VIII}} \quad (1)$$

where $T_{VII-VIII}$ is the mean temperature in July and August, P_{V-VII} and $P_{VII-VIII}$ are the precipitation sums from May to July and July to August, respectively. The FAI is based on observations of critical growth periods and was initially designed for the Hungarian climate and broadleaf tree

species. Nonetheless, the fundamental principle—that the period from May to August is crucial for growth—also applies to silver fir at our study sites.

2.2.2. Cross-dating and dendrochronological assessment of tree ring width series

To assess the reliability of the recorded TRW, ten series at each site were selected from dominant trees with clearly visible rings and a high correlation coefficient (≥ 0.7) with the rest of the selected trees, both overall and in 20-year segments. The TRW series were averaged to create a reference curve (master chronology) using CDendro software (Maxwell and Larsson, 2021). Additionally, pointer years were identified using the pointRes R package version 2.0.2 (Maaten-Theunissen et al., 2023). Overstory trees were chosen for these purposes as climatic conditions primarily influence their growth patterns, and they are less affected by competition compared to their counterparts in lower biosocial positions (Wang et al., 2023). The remaining increment cores were then tested against the reference curve, accepting the TRW series with a correlation coefficient of ≥ 0.5 . Series below this threshold underwent visual inspection and were included if pointer years matched growth trends of inspected TRW throughout the core length. Trees with shifts in pointer years indicating missing or false rings were excluded. TRW series were detrended using the spline function of the dplr R package (Bunn, 2022) with an adaptive smoothing spline rigidity of 0.7 times the series length and a wavelength cutoff of 0.5.

2.2.3. Calculation of the tree growth response to the drought stress

We used the framework of complementary resilience indices proposed by Lloret et al. (2011) to analyze the growth resilience (R_s) (Schwarz et al., 2020), defined as the ability of tree growth to return to pre-disturbance levels after experiencing a disturbance event (Eq. 2). According to this framework, growth resilience comprises two components: growth resistance (R_t) and recovery (R_c). Resistance refers to the ability to withstand unfavorable growing conditions (Eq. 3), while recovery refers to the ability to increase the growth rate after the disturbance compared to the growth during the stress year (Eq. 4).

$$R_s = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m TRW_{post,j} \times \frac{1}{m}}{\sum_{i=1}^n TRW_{pre,i} \times \frac{1}{n}} \quad (2)$$

$$R_t = \frac{TRW_{dist}}{\sum_{i=1}^n TRW_{pre,i} \times \frac{1}{n}} \quad (3)$$

$$R_c = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m TRW_{post,j} \times \frac{1}{m}}{TRW_{dist}} \quad (4)$$

where TRW_{dist} is growth during the disturbance (drought), $TRW_{pre,i}$ and $TRW_{post,j}$ growth in the i -th year pre- and j -th year post-disturbance correspondingly, n is the number of years pre-disturbance, m – number of years post-disturbance.

Even though the indices defined by Lloret et al. (2011) are considered the standard for analyzing drought stress growth reactions, they have notable limitations. The primary issue is that the recovery index mirrored the resistance index when trees were able to recover rapidly and fully after a drought (Schwarz et al., 2020); thus, the recovery index was not calculated in this research. Besides, Lloret complementary indices may provide an incomplete or misleading depiction of lagged drought responses or prolonged recovery times (Schwarz et al., 2020; Thurm et al., 2016). To address these issues, we calculated the total growth reaction (TGR) during the drought stress and recovery period compared to the pre-drought growth level (Eq. 5).

$$TGR = \sum_{j=1}^m \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n TRW_{pre,i}}{n} - TRW_{post,j} \right) + \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n TRW_{pre,i}}{n} - TRW_{dist} \quad (5)$$

The final piece of the puzzle missing in the literature is

understanding how drought-induced growth reduction compares to natural growth variability before drought stress. To address this, we introduce the stress-driven deviation index (SDD), a normalized metric based on the z-score formula (Eq. 6). The SDD quantifies how growth during a disturbance year deviates from pre-disturbance variability by scaling this difference against total absolute deviations and multiplying by the number of pre-disturbance years. A negative and positive SDD indicates growth reduction and increase, respectively, higher than the pre-disturbance average variability.

$$SDD = n \times \frac{TRW_{dist} - \frac{1}{n} \times \sum_{i=1}^n TRW_{pre,i}}{\sum_{i=1}^n |TRW_{pre,i} - \frac{1}{n} \times \sum_{i=1}^n TRW_{pre,i}|} \quad (6)$$

A reference period of four years was chosen for both pre- and post-disturbance. This duration was selected because most trees were capable of recovering their pre-drought growth within a year, and four years is the minimum period required to capture growth variability. Additionally, a four-year period avoids overlap with other extreme events that could affect the analysis.

2.2.4. Assessing of tree size diversity and admixture of broadleaf tree species

The Shannon diversity index (ShD) was used to describe the continuous tree size diversity based on 4-meter height classes (Kolisnyk et al., 2024a) (Eq. 7; Fig. 4). The basal area (BA) of all trees with a DBH bigger or equal to 7 cm and within each defined height class was summed to represent the class share. For instance, in the (4,8] class, the BA of all trees taller than 4 m but equal to or shorter than 8 m was summed and used as the proportion of trees in that class.

$$ShD = - \sum_{i=1}^N p_i \times \ln(p_i) \quad (7)$$

where N is the number of defined height classes, and p_i is the proportion of trees by BA in the i -th class.

The ShD and TBA values were normalized to a 0–1 scale at each site (ShD_{Norm} and TBA_{Norm}) to facilitate comparison across different sites using Eq. 8.

$$E_{Norm, k} = \frac{E_{k, s} - E_{min, s}}{E_{max, s} - E_{min, s}} \quad (8)$$

where $E_{k,s}$ is the stand characteristic of interest (ShD and TBA) on the plot k , site s , $E_{min,s}$ and $E_{max,s}$ are the minimum and maximum values of the characteristic at the site s , correspondingly.

The share of broadleaf tree species within each plot was determined by calculating the proportion of the total basal area represented by broadleaf species (Eq. 9).

$$Admix = \frac{BA_{broadleaf}}{BA_{all}} \quad (9)$$

Where $BA_{broadleaf}$ is the sum of the basal area of broadleaf trees, and BA_{all} is the total stand basal area. For trees not directly measured, heights were reconstructed using the Meyer height-DBH function (Meyer, 1940) (Supplementary Figure 1).

2.3. Statistical analysis

2.3.1. Modelling approach

The approach of sequential generalized linear mixed-effect models (GLMMs) was selected to address the increasing complexity of the four formulated hypotheses. By gradually introducing a more complex system of variables, we ensured that the primary effects were depicted before introducing additional ones. A random slope model (Eq. 10) was used to answer the first hypothesis to understand if there is a general trend between forest resilience parameters and tree size diversity across all sites. This approach accounts for potential differences in the

Fig. 4. Visual representation of tree distribution within the height classes used to calculate the ShD index. Two selected plots from the GE1 are shown, representing even-aged and uneven-aged stand structures. Trees are colored based on their height classes. In the even-aged plot, most trees are in the same or adjacent height classes, though certain level of vertical profile diversification is present due to the shade-tolerant nature of silver fir. In contrast, the uneven-aged stand shows a more random distribution of trees throughout the vertical profile.

relationship between explanatory and response variables at each site, thus avoiding within-site deviations from observed values and preventing over- or under-estimation of the explanatory variable's impact without the need to understand underlying cross-site differences.

$$y_{jk} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ShD_{Norm,jk} + u_{0j} + u_{1j} ShD_{Norm,jk} + u_{2k(j)} + \epsilon_{jk} \quad (10)$$

Where y_j are the response variables (Rt, Rs, TGR, SDD). β_0 is the model intercept, and β_n are the fixed parameters and their interaction coefficients. ShD_{Norm} stands for the normalized Shannon tree size diversity index, and Rt for resistance. u_{0j} is the random intercept and u_{1j} is the random slope for site j , and $u_{2k(j)}$ is the random intercept for the given tree k nested in the site j .

For hypothesis II, we expanded our analysis to include the site-specific climatic conditions (FAI) as fixed slopes (Eq. 11).

$$y_{jk} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ShD_{Norm,jk} + \beta_2 FAI_{jk} + \beta_3 (ShD_{Norm,jk} \times FAI_{jk}) + u_{0j} + u_{2k(j)} + \epsilon_{jk} \quad (11)$$

Hypothesis. III aimed to determine whether broadleaf tree species' admixture or stand density mediate tree size diversity's impact on resilience components. The admixture of broadleaf tree species ($Admix$) and the normalized stand total basal area (TBA_{Norm}) were introduced into the models to test this (Eq. 12).

$$y_{jk} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ShD_{Norm,jk} + \beta_2 FAI_{jk} + \beta_3 Admix_{jk} + \beta_4 (ShD_{Norm,jk} \times Admix_{jk}) + \beta_5 TBA_{Norm,jk} + \beta_6 (ShD_{Norm,jk} \times TBA_{Norm,jk}) + u_{0j} + u_{2k(j)} + \epsilon_{jk} \quad (12)$$

A top-down approach was selected to address hypothesis IV and determine whether the impact of tree size remains consistent over the tree size diversity gradient. As a first step, DBH was introduced as a parameter with interaction with ShD, using the most complex model structure for the given response variable as the base (Eq. 13). In the second step, backward stepwise regression was employed to determine if

the best-fitting model includes or excludes the interaction of DBH with ShD_{Norm} . The significance of the parameter and the AIC were compared to select the best-fitting model.

$$y_{jk} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ShD_{Norm,jk} + \beta_2 FAI_{jk} + \beta_3 DBH_{ijk} + \beta_4 (ShD_{Norm,jk} \times FAI_{jk} \times DBH_{ijk}) + u_{0j} + u_{2k(j)} + \epsilon_{jk} \quad (13)$$

2.3.2. Data transformation and GLMM family selection

Most of the existing literature uses untransformed, "raw" resilience component values for analysis of drought stress reaction (Dănescu et al., 2016; Gazol and Camarero, 2016; Lloret et al., 2011); however, in certain cases, this approach can be misleading. When assessing the impact of climatic drought on growth resilience components, the primary goal is determining whether trees have reacted to drought stress and, if so, the extent of their reaction. For instance, if Rt values exceed one, the tree has sustained growth under adverse conditions and even increased its growth rate. Values above one surpass a theoretical maximum and do not reflect growth resistance, defined as the tree's ability to maintain growth under deteriorated conditions, but rather other growth dynamics, such as enhanced growth due to improved photosynthesis with rising temperatures when water is not the main limiting factor. Similarly, as the Rs helps to understand whether a tree has returned to its pre-drought growth rate and, if not, the extent of the growth reduction, including values above one for both Rt and Rs can misrepresent phenomena beyond the scope of this study. To address this, the Rt and Rs values were capped at one (Fig. 5; Table 2) to retain critical information about the proportion of trees that did or did not react to the drought stress.

Furthermore, as positive SDD values indicate that growth during the disturbance year exceeds the pre-disturbance mean growth variability, SDD was limited to a maximum of value of zero. SDD values were then scaled using a min-max approach (Eq. 8, Table 2) to facilitate model convergence and ensure numerical stability crucial for proper optimization. Conversely, TGR values were constrained to a minimum of zero (Table 2), as values below zero show no cumulative growth reduction

Fig. 5. Illustration of the impact of data transformation and model selection on predicted Rt values at site PL1 in 2006.

Table 2
Summary of model specifications and transformations for components of growth resilience.

Component of growth resilience	Theoretical range	Transformation applied and resulting range	GLMM distribution	Additional model parameters
Rt	$(0, +\infty)$	Capped to maximum 1 $(0, 1]$	Ordered beta	
Rs	$(0, +\infty)$	Capped to maximum 1 $(0, 1]$	Ordered beta	
TGR	$(-\infty, +\infty)$	Capped to minimum 0 $(0, +\infty]$	Gaussian	Zero-inflation parameter
SDD	$(-\infty, +\infty)$	Capped to maximum 0, min-max transformation $[0, 1]$	Ordered beta	

during and after the disturbance compared to the pre-drought period.

To address the bounded range of resistance, resilience, and transformed SDD values, we employed the ordered beta regression model developed by Kubinec (2023). This approach was preferred over the zero-one-inflated model for its simplicity and capacity to utilize all available data effectively. However, since TGR values do not have an upper limit, a zero-inflated model was used for the analysis. All models were fitted using the glmmTMB package in R, version 1.1.9 (Brooks et al., 2024), with optimization performed via the Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno (BFGS) algorithm (Brooks et al., 2017).

3. Results

3.1. Selected drought years

The current year growth rate of silver fir is mostly correlated with growing conditions from May to July across all study sites. In GE1 and IT1, the growth rate of silver fir is strongly linked with SPEI_2_July,

SPEI_2_June, and SPEI_3_July (Supplementary Table 1). However, in PL2, an even slightly higher correlation than SPEI_2_July and SPEI_3_July was observed with SPEI_5_September, indicating a relatively longer active growth period at this site. In contrast, in PL1, in addition to SPEI_2_July and SPEI_1_June, SPEI_6_July was also correlated with growth, thus signifying that water accumulated during the spring can be crucial for tree growth at this site. Based on the selected SPEI variations, the following years had an SPEI value of -1.5 or lower for at least two of these SPEI variations and were thus identified as drought years: 2003 and 2008 for GE1, 2018 for IT1, 2006 for PL1, and 2015 for PL2 (Supplementary Figure 2).

3.2. Response to the drought stress

We found no consistent impact of ShD_{Norm} on the growth resilience components (Rt, Rs, SDD, TGR) across sites (Eq. 10). The lack of a general trend indicates that tree size diversity alone does not uniformly affect growth resilience components across all sites. However, when the site-specific effect of water availability, expressed through the FAI, is introduced in the model (Eq. 11), tree size diversity significantly impacts Rt and SDD (Fig. 6; Table 3), but not Rs and TGR. The intercept for Rt and SDD increases with FAI (Fig. 6), indicating that, on average, as climate aridity increases, trees reduce their growth rate during drought more than in relatively humid climates compared to their average pre-disturbance growth rate and variability. Moreover, the slope of the relationship between individual tree Rt or SDD and the stand ShD_{Norm} depends on the value of the FAI. For a relatively high FAI, which represents the water-limited site PL1, Rt, and SDD show a marked increase with increasing ShD_{Norm} . Conversely, as the FAI decreases, this relationship flattens and can even show downtrends, as observed at the FAI levels of the highly water-rich site GE1 (Fig. 6).

When TBA_{Norm} and Admix are sequentially introduced in the GLMM with an interaction with ShD_{Norm} (Eq. 12), they do not yield significance in any model describing resilience components. Thus, the admixture of broadleaf tree species and stand density does not mediate the impact of tree size diversity on the growth resilience components.

Similarly, the impact of DBH is not significant, when gradually incorporated into the model with an interaction term for tree size diversity. However, when DBH is added only with an interaction with the

Fig. 6. Predictions of the growth resistance (Rt) and stress-driven deviation (SDD) indices (thick lines) based on normalized tree size diversity (ShD_{Norm}) and levels of the Forest Aridity Index (FAI) representing our study sites (different colors). The 95 % confidence intervals are enclosed in the shaded areas between the thin lines.

Table 3
GLMM summary on the influence of ShD_{Norm} mediated by FAI on the growth resilience components (Rt and SDD).

Predictors	Rt			SDD		
	Estimates	CI	p	Estimates	CI	p
(Intercept)	53.10	15.87 – 188.45	< 0.001	28.67	10.53 – 72.90	< 0.001
FAI	0.40	0.24 – 0.65	< 0.001	0.50	0.41 – 0.70	< 0.001
ShD _{Norm} [sqrt]	0.21	0.06 – 0.69	0.011	0.27	0.09 – 0.77	0.033
FAI × ShD _{Norm} [sqrt]	1.75	1.22 – 2.37	0.002	1.53	1.09 – 1.94	0.021
Random Effects						
σ ²	0.03	0.05				
τ ₀₀	0.11 ID2:Location	< 0.01 ID2:Location				
	0.17 Location	0.02 Location				
ICC	0.90	0.31				
N	485 ID2	483 ID2				
	4 Location	4 Location				
Observations	592	590				
Marginal R ²	0.496	0.696				

Fig. 7. Predictions of the growth resistance (Rt) and stress-driven deviation (SDD) indices (thick lines) based on the DBH in cm and levels of the Forest Aridity Index (FAI) representing our study sites (different colors). The 95 % confidence intervals are enclosed in the shaded areas between the thin lines.

FAI (without tree size diversity), it becomes significant for Rt and SDD, but not for Rs and TGR. With a relatively high FAI representing the water-limited site PL1, Rt and SDD show a marked decrease with increasing DBH. Conversely, as the FAI decreases, this relationship flattens and can even show uptrends, as observed at the FAI levels of the water-rich site GE1 (Fig. 7; Table 4).

4. Discussion

4.1. Positive or neutral: exploring niche complementarity and mediating role of growth limiting factors

The growth of trees can be modulated by the structural organization of canopy and root systems, reduced within stand layer density and individual tree competition, as well as the general increase in resource acquisition efficiency and availability caused by the tree size diversification (Binkley et al., 2013; Bolte et al., 2010, 2013; Vanhellefont et al., 2018; Ali, 2019; Forrester, 2019), especially during resource scarcity (Chu et al., 2009; Jucker et al., 2016). Intensive management required to maintain the uneven-aged structure (O'Hara, 2014) modify intra- and inter-specific levels of competition, and increase resource availability for individual trees during extreme events (Forrester, 2019). As a result, structurally diverse stands are believed to have higher growth resistance and resilience to adverse climatic influences (Gazol and Camarero, 2016). Most of existing studies report positive or neutral impacts of uneven-aged silviculture or resulting tree size diversification on silver fir's growth resilience and stability.

Manetti and Cutini (2006) conducted research on forest structures' impact on the individual tree growth performance in the Apennines, Italy, and found that even-aged stands had more pointer years, suggesting lower resilience, while multilayered, uneven-aged forests exhibited more stable radial growth. Podlaski (2021) corroborated this by noting more homogeneous growth in silver fir individuals from uneven-aged stands. In earlier work, Podlaski (2018) found that diversifying tree sizes in forest patches enhances the resistance and resilience of silver fir-dominated forests against disturbances, such as high atmospheric SO₂ concentrations, by facilitating rapid recovery and stable growth post-depression. Cavlovic et al. (2015) theorized that reactive management and high mortality rates due to high SO₂ levels in the late 20th century resulted in the current forest structure and prevalence of

younger fir generations in the Dinaric region. Čater and Levanič (2013) also found more stable radial growth in silver fir under a single-tree selection management system compared to group selection, particularly during the general growth depression between 1960 and 1990.

In contrast to the previous studies, Dănescu et al. (2018) and Gazol and Camarero (2016) designed the research specifically to examine silver fir's growth resilience across the gradient of stand structures. Gazol and Camarero (2016) reported only minor impacts of tree size diversity on radial growth stability when examining silver fir responses to drought stress across a structural diversity gradient in the Central Spanish Pyrenees. Similarly, Dănescu et al. (2018) found no significant effects of tree size heterogeneity on the growth stability, resistance, and resilience of silver fir to summer drought stress in Germany.

However, the aforementioned studies are primarily based on single sites or sites with similar growing conditions, which limits broader interpretation. Addressing this gap, our findings demonstrate that the influence of tree size diversity on the drought resilience components of silver fir growth is contingent upon climatic conditions (Fig. 6). The impact of the tree size diversity on the growth resilience components is positive in places with limited water while flattening and becoming slightly negative with increasing water availability. This reconciles the divergent results within the existing literature and underscores the necessity of considering the ecological traits of a given species across a broader environmental context. Our findings are in line with the stress-gradient hypothesis that facilitation in plant communities is more frequent under strong abiotic stress relative to more favorable growing conditions (Bertness and Callaway, 1994; Maestre et al., 2009) and expand this notion to encompass tree size diversification

In more light-limited systems (where the amount and spatiotemporal distribution of plant-available below-ground resources like water or nutrients are sufficient to sustain growth during the whole vegetative season, such as GE1), stand growth tends to be size-asymmetric. Conversely, in systems where belowground resources are scarce (such as PL1), growth tends to become size-symmetric or inverse asymmetric (Pretzsch and Biber, 2010). Dominant trees may profit more, in terms of the growth rate from tree size diversification, in light-limited sites due to the improvement in prevailing resource limitations (Pretzsch and Biber, 2010). Tree size diversity allows for aboveground clustering and creates additional space (Godlee et al., 2021), enabling dominant trees to suppress the growth of younger generations by seizing a disproportionate amount of light, resulting in asymmetric growth patterns (Metsaranta and Loeffers, 2010; Yi et al., 2022). Thus, dominant trees with extended growth not limited by nutrient or water availability can theoretically use the maximum growing season and compensate for the loss in the number of "large" growth contributors compared to even-aged patches, resulting in strong positive growth dominance. However, this strategy does not improve water availability or water use efficiency; thus, the relative growth of individual trees may deteriorate more in structurally diverse stands during drought years as water becomes the growth-limiting factor.

Water-limited systems exhibit the contrasting dynamics. Below-ground resource scarcity contributes to symmetric or inverse asymmetric growth types as these resources are rapidly diffused and difficult for larger individuals to monopolize (Pretzsch and Biber, 2010). Thus, the abundance of younger generations and dominant trees with symmetrically higher growth rates may not bridge the productivity gap, and diversification of tree sizes may create negative growth dominance. This adaptational functional distribution between trees of different sizes maximizes the effects of tree size heterogeneity and resulting below-ground stratification. Reduced competition for water allows for sustained relative growth during extreme water scarcity events (Dănescu et al., 2016; Forrester, 2019). Thus, tree size heterogeneity and resulting belowground stratification in water-limited ecosystems positively influence the relative growth resilience of forest stands to drought stress (Figs. 6, 8).

Table 4
GLMM summary on the influence of DBH on the growth resilience components Rt, SDD.

Predictors	Rt			SDD		
	Estimates	CI	p	Estimates	CI	p
(Intercept)	22.72	3.48 – 148.49	0.001	6.43	1.45 – 28.56	0.014
FAI	0.56	0.32 – 0.98	0.043	0.93	0.59 – 1.45	0.736
DBH [sqrt]	1.16	1.00 – 1.34	0.046	1.31	1.12 – 1.52	0.001
ShD _{Norm} [sqrt]	0.22	0.07 – 0.71	0.012	0.29	0.09 – 0.95	0.041
FAI × DBH [sqrt]	0.94	0.90 – 0.98	0.008	0.90	0.85 – 0.94	< 0.001
FAI × ShD _{Norm} [sqrt]	1.73	1.22 – 2.44	0.002	1.48	1.03 – 2.11	0.032
Random Effects						
σ ²	0.03			0.05		
τ ₀₀	0.10	ID2:Location		< 0.01	ID2:Location	
	0.19	Location		0.04	Location	
ICC	0.90			0.46		
N	485	ID2		483	ID2	
Observations	592			590		
Marginal R ²	0.485			0.688		

Fig. 8. Schematic representation of a hypothetical resource acquisition strategy along a structural gradient. In systems with scarce belowground resources, water and nutrient use efficiency (a) and growth stability (c) increases with structural diversity. Similarly, in “light-limited” systems, solar radiation use efficiency increases (b); however, growth stability remains intact (c).

4.2. Lack of mediation effects of admixture and stand density on the growth resilience

While tree size diversity can enhance spatial resource-use stratification, species diversity and mixing are thought to reduce overall competition for scarce resources through both spatial and temporal stratification (Forrester, 2014; Loreau and Hector, 2001). The underlying principle involves interspecific complementarity, including competitive reduction (where intraspecific competition is stronger than interspecific competition) and facilitation (where one species supports the functioning of another) (Bottero et al., 2021; Forrester, 2014; Gillerot et al., 2021; Loreau and Hector, 2001). Although mixing broadleaf species is crucial for supporting silver fir survival in early developmental stages, due to soil acidification in monodominant stands (Becker and Drapier, 1984; Kolisnyk et al., 2024b), it does not significantly aid in growth facilitation through temporal competitive reduction.

Beech, an anisohydric species (Leuschner, 2020; Pretzsch et al., 2013), maintains open stomata and high photosynthetic rates during stress events longer than silver fir, which closes its stomata earlier during droughts to reduce the risk of cavitation (Jones and Sutherland, 1991). While this strategy allows beech to continue accessing water longer into a drought by risking morphological changes (Jones and Sutherland, 1991; Pretzsch et al., 2013), it does not alter silver fir's response to stress. Hence, although there is temporal stratification between these species, it does not result in a complementarity that benefits fir and does not mediate the impact of the tree size diversification.

Additionally, spatial clustering resulting from mixing tree species, which is frequently suggested to improved drought resistance (del Río et al., 2017; Hilmers et al., 2019; Jones and Sutherland, 1991), inherently leads to increased tree size diversity. For instance, Ray et al. (2023) noted that species diversity in controlled even-aged stands leads to increased structural complexity. This intrinsic connection between species mixture and tree size diversity also explains the absence of a mediation effect of broadleaf species admixture on the relationship between tree size diversity and growth resilience components in our modeling approach. Thus, even though integrating broadleaf species is essential for stable ecosystem functioning in silver-fir-dominated forests, such as regeneration (Paluch and Jastrzębski, 2013), it has neutral effects on the growth resilience of silver fir to drought stress.

Surprisingly, the TBA similarly neither modulated nor complemented the model's estimation of the impact of tree size diversity on growth resilience components. Stand density is considered a primary

driver of resource competition (Mina et al., 2018; Power et al., 2019; Vallet and Pérot, 2011), significantly influencing tree growth (Steckel et al., 2020). It is commonly believed that reducing TBA can accelerate tree growth (Steckel et al., 2020) and reduce growth sensitivity to short-term fluctuations in environmental conditions (Giuggiola et al., 2013). This reduction can also help moderate the effects of drought-induced stress by increasing the resource availability per individual (Steckel et al., 2020). Factors contributing to this include reduced water transpiration through the larger leaf area (Boncina et al., 2007; Bréda et al., 1995) and the development of root systems reaching deeper soil profiles (Aussenac and Granier, 1988), which may increase water availability and water use efficiency under reduced competition (Steckel et al., 2020). However, multiple studies have also shown the opposing effects of lower stand densities and report decreased plant-available water due to increased evapotranspiration losses from higher wind speeds and penetration of solar radiation in recently thinned stands (Aussenac, 2000; Brooks and Mitchell, 2011; Steckel et al., 2020). These opposing mechanisms might counterbalance each other and are likely rooted in several confounding factors (Steckel et al., 2020).

4.3. Impact of the tree size

Tree growth and reactions to unfavorable growing conditions are metabolically influenced by tree size (Niinemets, 2010). Our findings show that smaller trees have higher resistance (R_t and SDD) under stronger water limitations, such as at sites like PL1 (Fig. 7). As water availability increases, this trend changes, resulting in a flattened relationship or even a slight increase in R_t and SDD with increasing DBH.

These findings align with previous studies on silver fir and other shade-tolerant European tree species. Smaller individuals are typically less efficient in light usage (Gspaltl et al., 2013; Zeller and Pretzsch, 2019) or resource utilization in general (Assman, 1961; Assmann, 1970; Zeller and Pretzsch, 2019). While younger, smaller trees have smaller volume increments, they are believed to be more resistant and resilient to external influences in terms of relative growth change (Cavlovic et al., 2015; Lebourgeois et al., 2014; Pretzsch et al., 2018), as in absolute terms the growth of smaller individuals is already metabolically limited (Assman, 1961). For instance, silver fir and beech individuals with larger diameters can have a higher sensitivity to drought stress during active growth (Mérián and Lebourgeois, 2011), as their demand for water supply is elevated due to increased exposure to radiation and high temperatures due to their biosocial position (Bréda et al., 2006; Mérián

and Lebourgeois, 2011). Under cold and wet climates, conifers respond similarly among size-diameter classes (Meyer and Bräker, 2001). This phenomenon can be attributed to the lower biosocial position of smaller individuals of shade-tolerant species, such as fir, and the resulting benefits of micro-climatic variations, including buffered temperature variations under the canopy, reduced thermal stress, and transpiration during summer (Aussenac, 2000; Mérian and Lebourgeois, 2011; Pretzsch et al., 2018).

The slight positive slope for the impact of increasing DBH in water-rich sites can, counterintuitively but similarly to the effects of the tree size diversity on the growth resilience components, be explained by size-asymmetric growth (Pretzsch et al., 2018). Dominant trees seize a disproportionate amount of resources in light-limited systems (Pretzsch and Biber, 2010), and we believe that this behavior can be sustained during water scarcity events. The phenological adaptations of the trees that are normally not limited by water availability, including developed crown structures and fine roots, but most importantly, needle functional adaptability does not disappear with drought stress. The levels of stomatal conductance of silver fir needles are the results of ecophysiological adaptations to climatic conditions (Peguero-Pina et al., 2007; Robakowski et al., 2003). Thus, larger trees may sustain the level of their functioning, acting more like anisohydric species than those in arid sites. While this strategy seems effective in the comparatively low severity of drought stress analyzed in water-rich sites, it increases the risk of cavitation during severe droughts.

We also found that the tree size diversity did not modify the impact of individual tree size on the growth resilience components. Nevertheless, it remains uncertain whether differences in tree responses to stressors can be attributed solely to size-related physiological characteristics (Anderson-Teixeira et al., 2022; Coomes and Allen, 2007) or if the trees' biosocial positions played a crucial role (Pretzsch et al., 2018). Despite including even-aged stands of various ages at each site, we solely focused on pre-mature (40–80 years old) or mature even-aged stands (100–140 years old). Thus, data for the smallest suppressed trees were obtained from individuals growing beneath the canopy, which do not represent all the possible tree size-biosocial position combinations.

4.4. Components of forest resilience

Some components of forest resilience did not exhibit any connection with the stand characteristics we examined, while others did. This does not imply a contradiction among the components or diminish their utility. In contrast, as Lloret et al., (2011) described, these components serve as complementary indices, each highlighting distinct aspects of growth resilience. For example, neither the Rs nor the TGR was affected by any stand characteristic, mainly because silver fir typically responds to the growing conditions of the current year (Michelot et al., 2012), and post-drought years usually provided favorable conditions, enabling most trees to restore their growth to pre-disturbance levels.

The introduction of the SDD supplements the analysis by addressing aspects of growth resilience that were previously overlooked. However, this approach also presents limitations. Much like the resistance, resilience, and recovery indices proposed by Lloret et al. (2011), carefully selecting the pre-drought period is essential to ensure that it is long enough to capture variability but does not include the impact of other extreme events, such as droughts or early frosts.

5. Conclusions

Under more extreme climate scenarios, conditions may rapidly become increasingly arid in some parts of the natural range of silver fir (López-Tirado et al., 2024). This scenario presents a binary choice for sustained ecosystems and their management: gradually adapt or face abrupt replacement with more suitable species under emerging climate. The latter could result in the uncontrolled development of biotic disturbance agents and outbreaks (Pietrzykowski and Woś, 2021),

undermining the core pillars of sustainable silviculture, including CO₂ storage in growing stock (Favero et al., 2021).

Silver fir demonstrates considerable plasticity and can align life strategy with prevailing growing conditions (Dobrowolska et al., 2017; Robakowski et al., 2003). We found that the impact of tree size diversity on the growth resilience of silver fir to drought stress is contingent upon the site's long-term climatic conditions and growth-limiting factors. On sites with water limitations, tree size diversity significantly improves resistance to drought stress. Conversely, increasing water availability makes this relationship less pronounced or even slightly negative. A similar pattern is observed regarding the impact of tree size: smaller trees exhibit a greater resistance to drought stress than their larger counterparts in water-limited sites, but as water availability increases, this trend flattens and reverses. Ecophysiological adaptations to prevailing growing conditions, which foster symmetric competition for resources in water-limited sites and more asymmetric competition with increased water availability, may partially explain the influence of tree size diversity and individual tree size on silver fir's response to drought stress. Notably, the admixture of broadleaf tree species and stand density did not modulate the effect of tree size diversity on growth resilience components.

Efforts to increase beta diversity and irregular structure by reducing the size of extensive clear-cutting, creating canopy openings for group selection systems, and enhancing species diversity are underway in European forests to mitigate growing risk. However, implementing uneven-aged forestry and increasing tree size diversity (and thus alpha diversity) is considered relatively challenging. Since tree size diversity is particularly crucial on more arid sites, it can be regarded as a strategic management tool to adapt silver fir-dominated forests to anticipated global change.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Uhl Enno: Writing – original draft, Resources. **Wellstein Camilla:** Writing – original draft, Resources. **Bingham Logan:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Czacharowski Marcin:** Writing – original draft. **Bielak Kamil:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Drozdowski Stanisław:** Writing – original draft, Resources. **Kolisnyk Bohdan:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Funding sources

This project was funded by the Marie Skłodowska Curie Skill-for. Action programme under Grant Agreement No. 956355. Furthermore, the work was also partially supported by the Polish Government (MNiSW) under Grant Agreement No. 566953/PnH 2/2023 and by the Science Development Fund of the Warsaw University of Life Sciences-SGGW.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used OpenAI ChatGPT and Grammarly in order to improve the clarity and coherence of the manuscript. After using the tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to the two anonymous reviewers for their thoughtful feedback. Our thanks also go to the early-stage researchers from the Skill-for.Action project, particularly Przemyslaw Jankowski, Shamim Ahmed, and Daniel Minikaev, whose support and fruitful discussions were invaluable in shaping the manuscript and completing the fieldwork. We are also grateful to our partners at the Free University of Bolzano and the Technical University of Munich for their collaboration, assistance with data collection, and shared insights. Special thanks go to Julia Schmucker for her active help with the plot selection and measurements. We also acknowledge the foresters who generously permitted us to conduct research in their forests, making this study possible. Finally, we extend our appreciation to the team at the Department of Silviculture at the Warsaw University of Life Science, especially Zdzisława Widawska, Longina Ożga, Wojciech Ożga, Leszek Bolibok, Michał Dzwonkowski, and Henryk Szeligowski, for their invaluable support.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.foreco.2025.122765](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2025.122765).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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